
PREVALENCE AND CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS OF DRUG-DRUG INTERACTIONS IN PSYCHIATRIC PATIENTS ATTENDING FEDERAL NEURO PSYCHIATRIC HOSPITAL, MAIDUGURI

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ABSTRACT

Drug-drug interactions (DDIs) significantly impact patient safety in psychiatric care due to polypharmacy and comorbidities. It has been reported that 20 – 30% of all adverse reactions to drugs are caused by drug-drug interactions, which can be prevented through appropriate monitoring and follow up. This study investigated the prevalence of DDIs among patients at the Federal Psychiatric Hospital, Maiduguri, Nigeria, using six online DDI checkers (Medscape, Epocrates, Lexi-Drug, Drug Bank, Drugs.com, and WEBMD). 541 prescriptions were analysed with a high prevalence of major DDIs (38.1%). The findings suggest a strong association between polypharmacy, comorbidities, and DDI risk. This study emphasizes the need for comprehensive DDI management strategies, including routine monitoring and the use of multiple DDI software programs to enhance patient safety. Continuous training for healthcare providers, accurate medication histories, and multicenter studies to validate these findings and explore DDIs in other settings are also recommended. By incorporating DDI checkers and mitigating DDI risks, healthcare professionals can improve patient safety and treatment outcomes.

Keywords: Drug-drug interactions (DDIs), psychiatric patients, polypharmacy, comorbidities, psychiatric care, Nigeria.

Introduction

A drug-drug interaction can be defined as the pharmacological response to the administration or co-exposure of one drug with another drug that modifies the response of patients to the drug effect (Malone *et al.*, 2015). The consequences of clinically significant pDDIs have a negative impact on the morbidity, mortality, duration of hospitalization, quality of life, and healthcare costs of the patients (Guthrie *et al.*, 2015).

It has been reported that 20 – 30% of all adverse reactions to drugs are caused by drug-drug interactions, which can be prevented through appropriate monitoring and follow up. But this incidence increases among the elderly and patients who take two or more medications (Kannan *et al.*, 2013). In inpatients, the risk of having potentially interacting drug combinations can additionally increase because new drugs are often added to the existing drug therapy (Heininger-Rothbucher *et al.*

2012). DDIs are a concern for patients and providers, as polypharmacy is becoming more common in managing complex diseases or comorbidities and the consequences can range from untoward effects to drug-related morbidity and mortality (Balidemaj *et al.*, 2021). Prescription drug interactions are a significant concern in psychiatric practice due to the complex pharmacotherapy often required for patients with mental health disorders. The concurrent use of multiple medications, including antipsychotics, mood stabilizers, antidepressants, and anxiolytics, increases the risk of potential drug interactions, which can lead to adverse effects, reduced therapeutic efficacy, or compromised patient safety (Reutfors *et al.*, 2016). Psychiatric patients often present with complex clinical profiles, requiring polypharmacy to manage their symptoms effectively. However, this complexity increases the risk of drug interactions, as multiple medications may interact with each other pharmacokinetically or pharmacodynamically (Tamburello *et al.*, 2020). Drug interactions in psychiatric patients can have profound effects on patient safety and treatment outcomes. Adverse interactions may lead to exacerbation of psychiatric symptoms, increased hospitalizations, or the need for additional interventions to manage side effects (Hefner *et al.*, 2018). By identifying and mitigating potential interactions, healthcare providers can improve patient care and reduce the risk of harm. Online drug interaction checkers are valuable tools for healthcare professionals to screen for potential interactions between medications. These tools utilize extensive databases of

drug-drug interactions and provide rapid assessments of the compatibility of prescribed medications (Palleria *et al.*, 2013). Incorporating multiple online checkers in a prescription analysis study can enhance the comprehensiveness and accuracy of the assessment. The findings of a prescription analysis study can inform quality improvement initiatives within psychiatric hospitals. By identifying common patterns of drug interactions and associated risk factors, healthcare institutions can develop targeted interventions, such as educational programs for prescribers or updates to clinical guidelines, to improve the safety and effectiveness of medication management (Lombardi *et al.*, 2019).

The primary objectives of this study were to determine the prevalence of DDIs in psychiatric patients at FPNH Maiduguri and to explore the clinical implications of these interactions. The findings aim to inform clinical practice and provide recommendations for improving patient safety and treatment efficacy.

Methodology

Study Setting and Study Design

This cross-sectional study was conducted at the Federal Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital (FNPH), which is in Maiduguri, Borno State. It is a regional Psychiatric Hospital, which serves the northeast region of Nigeria and receives influx of patients from the neighbouring countries of Chad, Cameroon, and Niger Republics. (Yusuf *et al.*, 2018).

Study Population and Sample Size Estimation

Sample size was determined using Fisher's formula

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{d^2}$$

Where:

n is the sample size

Z is the standard normal value at confidence interval of 95% = 1.96,

P is proportion taken at 0.5, and

d is precision or margin of sampling error tolerated (0.05).

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times (0.5) \times (1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2} = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{0.0025} = \frac{0.9604}{0.0025} = 384.16$$

After obtaining the estimated minimum sample size, more folders of eligible patients that were readily available during the time of the data collection were added to the study population until a total number of 541 folders were reviewed.

Ethical Approval

The proposal for this research was submitted to the Hospital Research and Ethics Committee and ethical approval with reference number: FNPH/062023/REC138 was granted before the commencement of the study. Information about the clients was kept strictly confidential and were not disclosed to any third party. The confidentiality of this information was considered the exclusive right of the clients, and as such, it was handled with the utmost trust and discretion. The data collected were exclusively used for research purposes.

Data Collection and Sampling Technique

The current prescriptions of 541 patients were extracted from their medical folders (every clinic day for a period of 3 months) and analyzed for potential drug-drug interaction using 6 different online drug interaction checkers —Medscape, Drug

bank, Epocrates, Lexi drug, Drugs.com, and WEBMD. A data collection form was used to extract the sociodemographic data, clinical information and current medications prescribed from each folder before screening with the six different DDI checkers. Convenience sampling was used in folder selection and only the folders of adult patients who were prescribed more than one medication were included in the study. Results obtained from all six checkers were recorded and analysed for level of severity to select those with major DDI from the total number of potential DDIs that were flagged.

Data Analysis

The prevalence of DDIs was calculated based on the number of prescriptions containing major interactions. Data were analysed using Statistical Products for Service Solutions (SPSS) version 25.0; SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA (Saleh, 2023) after checking for errors and coding to numerical values. Mann-Whitney U-test was used (for variables of two categories) while Krustal-Wallis test was used (for variables with more than two categories) to

determine the difference in occurrence of major DDI with each patient characteristic parameter. A P -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant (95% Confidence Interval). Univariate analysis was conducted to see the effect of independent variables on the outcome variable. And variables which showed P value less than 0.2 were considered for multivariate analysis.

Results

The characteristics of the patients that made up this study population is presented in Table 1. Majority of the patients were: aged 20-34 (55.27%), females (50.28%), married (53.05%), had no formal education (61.92%), unemployed (52.68%) and had no other comorbidity (69.32%). Patients' Median age was 30 years. The clinical assessment of the patients is shown in Table 2. Patients with Schizophrenia spectrum disorders comprised 24.58% of the total study population. This is followed by patients with depressive disorders (20.70%). According to the result shown in Table 3, from the 541 prescriptions reviewed, 206 (38.07%) drug interactions were identified as clinically relevant drug-drug interactions. Among these, 95 (46.12%) were detected by DrugBank, while Epocrates, Medscape and WebMD identified 7 (3.40%) each and Lexi-Drug identified 5 (2.43%) respectively. The factors associated with major drug-drug-interaction are presented in Table 4. Mann-Whitney U-test was used (for variables of two categories) while Kruskal-Wallis test was used (for variables with more than two categories) to determine the difference in major DDI based on each patient characteristic parameter. A P -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant (95% Confidence Interval). Comorbidity

was significantly associated with major drug-drug interaction and the number of drugs prescribed was also found to be significantly associated with major drug-drug interaction (with those having more than 3 drugs showing a much higher level of association). The predictors for the presence of major DDIs in each prescription are depicted in Table 5. In the multivariate model, Patients with comorbidities, such as cardiovascular diseases or diabetes, exhibited a higher prevalence of major DDIs compared to those without comorbidities. The adjusted odds ratio for DDI occurrence in patients with comorbidities was 2.12 (95% CI, 1.44–3.14). Similarly, the adjusted odds ratio for DDI occurrence in patients with polypharmacy was 1.84 (95% CI, 1.13–2.99), indicating a strong association between polypharmacy and DDI risk (as those with a prescription having more than three medications were 1.8 times more likely to have a major DDI compared to those with fewer medications prescribed).

Discussion

Patient Characteristics

The demographic and social characteristics of the study population provide critical context for interpreting the results. Most of the patients were aged 20-34 years, with a median age of 30 years, suggesting that young adults constitute a significant proportion of the population requiring psychiatric care. This finding aligns with global trends where mental health disorders often manifest prominently in early adulthood. Furthermore, the predominance of females (50.28%) and married individuals (53.05%) underscores the need for gender-sensitive and family-inclusive approaches in mental health interventions.

A notable proportion of the participants (61.92%) had no formal education, and over half (52.68%) were unemployed. These socio-economic factors likely exacerbate the burden of mental health disorders and present additional barriers to accessing quality care. Addressing these systemic inequities is critical for improving health outcomes within this demographic.

Clinical Assessments

The clinical distribution of psychiatric disorders revealed that schizophrenia spectrum disorders (24.58%) and depressive disorders (20.70%) were the most prevalent diagnoses. These findings are consistent with existing literature highlighting the significant global burden of these conditions. Schizophrenia spectrum disorders often require long-term pharmacological management, which may increase the risk of drug-drug interactions (DDIs). Similarly, depressive disorders frequently involve polypharmacy, further emphasizing the importance of careful prescription monitoring.

Clinically Relevant Drug-Drug Interactions

Among the 541 prescriptions reviewed, 38.07% contained clinically relevant DDIs. This relatively high prevalence underscores the importance of vigilant pharmacovigilance in psychiatric care settings. The substantial contribution of Drug Bank (46.12%) in detecting clinically relevant DDIs compared to Epocrates, Medscape, WebMD, and Lexi-Drug highlights variability in the sensitivity of DDI detection tools. This variability indicates a potential need for standardizing DDI identification protocols in clinical practice to enhance patient safety.

Factors Associated with Major DDIs

The Mann-Whitney U-test and Kruskal-Wallis test provided robust statistical analyses of the factors influencing major DDIs. Comorbidity emerged as a significant factor, with patients having additional medical conditions such as cardiovascular diseases or diabetes being more likely to experience major DDIs. This finding is supported by the adjusted odds ratio of 2.12, indicating that comorbidities more than double the risk of DDIs. These results highlight the importance of integrating multidisciplinary care approaches to mitigate risks in patients with complex medical histories. Polypharmacy was another critical factor associated with increased DDI risk. Patients prescribed more than three medications were 1.84 times more likely to encounter major DDIs. This finding underscores the need for prescribing practices that prioritize medication optimization and deprescribing where possible. Implementing clinical decision support systems and regular medication reviews could significantly reduce the prevalence of DDIs in this high-risk group.

While this study provides valuable insights, some limitations warrant consideration. The reliance on specific DDI detection tools may have led to underestimation or overestimation of clinically relevant DDIs. Additionally, the cross-sectional nature of the study limits the ability to establish causality. Longitudinal studies are therefore recommended for further insight regarding DDI prevalence at FNPH Maiduguri.

This study has demonstrated that drug-drug interactions are prevalent in psychiatric patients at FNPH Maiduguri, with polypharmacy and comorbidities serving as

significant risk factors. The findings of this study highlight the importance of implementing a comprehensive approach to DDI management in psychiatric care as well as the need for a proactive approach to DDI management in psychiatric care, particularly for patients with complex medication needs. By incorporating multiple DDI checker tools, clinicians can gain a broader perspective on potential interactions and reduce the likelihood of adverse effects. Additionally, this study

emphasizes the need for healthcare providers to prioritize DDI management in high-risk groups, including patients with comorbidities and those on complex drug regimens.

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Table 1: Characteristics of patients attending FNPH Maiduguri

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Age Group		
< 20	40	7.39
20 - 34	299	55.27
35 - 44	92	17.01
> 45	110	20.33
Total	541	100
Gender		
Male	269	49.72
Female	272	50.28
Total	541	100
Marital Status		
Single	195	36.05
Married	287	53.05
Widowed	29	5.36
Divorced	30	5.54
Total	541	100
Highest Qualification		
None	335	61.92
FSL	26	4.80
SSCE	118	21.81
BSc/Diploma	59	10.90
MSc	3	0.57
Total	541	100
Employment		
Unemployed	285	52.68
Employed	247	45.65
Retired	9	1.67
Total	541	100
Comorbidity		
Yes	166	30.68
No	375	69.32
Total	541	100

Table 2: Clinical Assessment of Patients attending FNPH Maiduguri

Diagnosis	Frequency	Percent
Schizophrenia spectrum disorders	133	24.58
Seizure disorders	81	14.97
Bipolar related disorders	62	11.46
Depressive illness	112	20.70
Mental and behavioral disorder secondary to substance(s) use	54	9.98
Headaches	20	3.69
Organic mental illness	20	3.69
Cognitive disorders	16	2.95
Anxiety disorders	5	0.94
Others	38	7.04
Total	541	100

Table 3: Major DDIs detected from prescriptions of patients attending FNPH Maiduguri

DDI Checker	Major DDI Detected	Percentage (%)
Medscape	7	3.39
Drugbank	95	46
Epocrates	7	3.39
Lexicomp	5	2.43
Drugs.com	85	41.26
Web MD	7	3.39
Total	206	100

N = 541

Table 4: Factors Associated with major drug-drug interaction in patients attending FNPH Maiduguri

Variable	Mean rank	P value
^μ Age Group		
< 20	357.23	0.34
20 - < 35	349.56	
35 - < 45	322.18	
> 45	345.60	
^Ω Gender		
Male	365.14	0.002*
Female	330.0	
^Ω Marital Status		
Single	343.81	0.69
Married	346.02	
Widowed	376.92	
Divorced	344.24	
^Ω Highest Qualification		
None	359.51	0.02*
FSL	349.66	
SSCE	326.92	
BSc/Diploma/ MSc	313.03	
^μ Employment		
Unemployed	352.12	0.23
Employed	337.88	
^μ Comorbidity		
Yes	389.48	<0.001*
No	332.94	
^μ Number of prescribed medications		
≤ 3	340.32	0.006*
> 3	387.32	

μ: Mann-Whitney test

Ω: Kruskal-Wallis test

*significant at p<0.05

Table 5: Predictors of major DDIs from prescription analysis of patients attending FNPH Maiduguri

Parameter	Major DDI		Univariate			Multivariate		
	Yes	No	cOR	95% CI,	P value	aOR	95% CI,	P value
Age								
< 20	36	94			ref			
20 - < 35	89	116	0.87	0.56 – 1.37	0.56			
35 - < 45	17	80	0.54	0.29 – 1.05	0.07			
> 45	27	82	0.86	0.48 -1.54	0.61			
Gender								
Male	73	204			ref			
Female	96	168	0.59	0.42 – 0.84	0.003	0.68	0.45 – 1.02	0.06
Marital Status								
Single	66	161			ref			
Married	83	157	0.99	0.67 – 1.43	0.94			
Widowed	10	23	1.40	0.64 -3.09	0.40			
Divorced	10	31	1.68	0.81 – 3.46	0.16			
Highest Qualification								
None	108	180			ref			
FSL	12	36	0.67	0.31 – 1.46	0.27	0.64	0.29 – 1.42	0.27
SSCE	26	96	0.55	0.23 1.33	0.18	0.46	0.19 – 1.15	0.09
MSc/BSc/Diplom a	13	70	1.18	0.59 – 2.35	0.64	1.04	0.51 – 2.11	0.91
Employment								
Unemployed	110	208			ref			
Employed	58	165	0.75	0.52 – 1.08	0.12	1.09	0.71 – 1.68	0.69
Comorbidity								
No	87	288			ref			
Yes	61	105	2.33	1.59 – 3.40	<0.001	2.12	1.44 – 3.14	<0.001* *
Number of medications prescribed								
≤ 3	116	336			ref			
> 3	33	56	2.06	1.29 – 3.28	0.002	1.84	1.13 – 2.99	0.01*

** $P < 0.005$; * $P < 0.05$ Ref: reference; aOR: adjusted odds ratio; cOR: crude odds ratio; 95% CI: 95% confidence interval.